

TEACHING PHONETICS IN ENGLISH USING ACTUAL VIDEO MATERIALS IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This article provides features of teaching English phonetics based on authentic video materials in Medical Universities and gives levels of phonetics learning. In addition, it suggests several feasible notions from prominent pedagogues.

Keywords: *tool, video clips, factors, levels, colloquial idioms, frontal surveys.*

At this time, videos are the primary tool used to teach foreign languages to medical students of any skill level. Video excerpts from documentaries and feature films, TV news, cartoons, interviews, and video tours of museums and exhibition spaces should all be used in foreign language classrooms.

The instructional value of videos “lies in the possibility of visualizing theoretical material, specifying a model to follow due to the authenticity of the video resource, conducting interactive classes, increasing motivation to study the theoretical component of teaching the subject and organizing productive independent activity of medical students to form stable oral-pronouncing skills and oral-speech skills” [1].

A rare chance to study a foreign language from local speakers and become familiar with the historical background and way of life of the nation where the language is being studied is shown in the movie. A harmoniously developed medical student personality emerges in a multicultural setting through the use of real video clips that mimic the language environment and medical situation [2]. Medical students also develop their communicative, sociocultural, and sociolinguistic skills in other languages.

It should be mentioned that the combination of autonomous study, structured approaches to teaching English, and the unique function of an English teacher serving as a mentor, helper, and facilitator makes all of this feasible.

Carefully chosen real-world video clips enhance the way new instructional content is presented visually, help you learn phonetics, and help you construct phonetics. Medical students actively engage in a conscious imitation complex at the same time, mimicking the speech patterns of native speakers.

The ability of a video film or video fragment to leave an imprint and an emotional influence on medical student is its benefit. Medical students have the ability to explain not just what happened in the video they saw, but also the characters' emotions and overall tone as well as their own interpretations of what they observed. Because of this, the selection of video content is based on several factors, the most important of which being the alignment of the topics covered with the medical students' age, interests, and degree of foreign language competence as well as with the objectives of education.

The selection of video content is based on several factors, including professional conditioning, authenticity, and accessibility, variety of genres, and need and sufficiency of the content. When it comes to the medical system and native speakers' perspectives, real video content from a different culture is incredibly educational. It should be a further source of knowledge, have the capacity to educate and develop medical students, inspire them to learn a foreign language in medical sphere, and take into consideration each student's unique requirements, talents, skill level, and traits.

Achieving multidisciplinary and meta-disciplinary learning goals is aided by watching real-world videos. Medical students learn to think logically, which includes how to compare, contrast, analyze, and synthesize facts and phenomena as well as how to understand and generalize new information [3].

Using real-world video resources as a basis for our analysis, we discovered that the goal of learning English phonetics is to acquire the capacity to extract knowledge accurately and with the degree of comprehension required to complete a given educational assignment. Learning produces a free, developed, and educated personality that is prepared to use its knowledge, skills, and abilities for productive interactions with members of other cultures and societies. It also gives one a thorough understanding of socio-cultural orientation and the ability to interpret facts and phenomena and select appropriate speech and non-speech behavior in a variety of cultural contexts.

The design of the visual material, its compositional and semantic structure, and monological and dialogic forms of speech all have a significant impact on teaching phonetics in English. Other factors that impact phonetics instruction include the quantity and quality of presentations, the speaker's individual voice traits, the speech rate, the range of intonation shades, the irreversibility of auditory reaction, various information sources, and particular medical and cultural units of information.

The following levels of phonetics learning—“motivational-stimulating (the recipient's willingness to comprehend a speech utterance); analytical-synthetic (reception and decoding of video information); higher (understanding of the utterance)”—are thought to benefit from the use of video materials in the process [4]. Understanding may be defined as the listener's capacity to appropriately interpret what they have heard and convert the perceived idea into a contemplative state without appreciably losing the meaning that the speaker intended to convey. According to our research, pre-demonstration, demonstration, and post-demonstration phases should be included in phonetics instruction based on the utilization of video resources.

New terms and colloquial idioms are presented and solidified during the initial pre-demonstration phase. It is important to instruct medical students in information extraction based on the disclosure of medical and cultural units' meanings (socio-cultural realities). At this point, the instructor often assigns work that includes the video's title, keywords related to the issue the storyline addresses, and definitions of the genre of the content they've watched. The development of phonetic abilities, phonetic knowledge, and phonetic skill formation should be the primary areas of emphasis.

During the second demonstration stage, medical students actively participate in instructional activities while watching video content. Research on the establishment of phonetic skills, phonetic information acquisition, and phonetic skill development is still ongoing.

The third stage involves post-demonstration activities such as question-and-answer sessions (frontal surveys), role-playing dialogues and polylogues (work in microgroups), expanding and adding communication scenarios from the video, and transferring the situation into the medical students' daily lives (using learned phonetics in real-world professional settings).

In conclusion, it can be claimed that learning English phonetics is best achieved through the use of audiovisual resources. Assimilation of foreign language learning becomes more engaging, challenging, and emotionally charged when video resources are used to portray models of real-world language conversation. In addition to helping to assimilate background knowledge in a volume that is similar to that of a native speaker of the studied language and culture, videos that contain socio-cultural and medical information also aid in revealing the unique characteristics of the history, customs, and traditions of the nation where the language is studied and comparing them with their native culture. Utilizing real-world video content gives medical students plenty of opportunity to

actively engage in the process of creating and strengthening their phonetic abilities. It also boosts motivation and fosters an environment where medical students may work independently.

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